

Data Dictionary

Longitudinal ALS Cohort

Authors

Name	Organisation
Manfredo Atzori ¹	UNIPD ²
Marcos Casado Barbero ³	EMBL-EBI ⁴

Revision history

Version	Date	Authors	Document history/approvals
v1.1.1	22.11.2025	Manfredo Atzori	Review Data Dictionary and address comments.
v1.1.0	21.11.2025	Marcos Casado Barbero	Add Description; add DOI reference; fix wrong and missing terminologies, duplicated terms and truncated descriptions.
v1.0.1	19.11.2025	Marcos Casado Barbero	Format document for HEREDITARY.
v1.0.0	01.01.2024	Manfredo Atzori	Create Data Dictionary.

Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Description

This document provides the structured data dictionary for the Longitudinal ALS Cohort collected at the University of Padua (UNIPD), describing the variables and value definitions used in the cohort dataset. It is intended to accompany and document its Zenodo landing page. ⁵

Anagrafica (Personal information)

Field	Description
1. ID	Patient ID
2. id_name	Patient name
3. data di nascita	Birth date

¹ <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5397-2063>

² <https://ror.org/00240q980>

³ <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7747-6256>

⁴ <https://ror.org/02catss52>

⁵ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17671190>

Field	Description	
4. ULSS	Number of the local public health centre	
5. Info	Other information	
6. Sottotipo in anagrafica	Subtype	
	Values as follows:	
	SLA	Motor Neuron Disease / Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis
	PBP	Progressive Bulbar Palsy
	PLS	Primary Lateral Sclerosis
	SLA,tracheo	Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis, tracheostomy
	motoneurone	Motor Neuron Disease / Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis
	SLA, flail arm	Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis, flail arm syndrome
	sindrome BVVL	Brown-Vialetto-Van Laere syndrome
	PMA	Progressive Muscular Atrophy
	II MMN	Multifocal Motor Neuropathy
	S ALS	Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis
	UMN	Upper Motor Neuron syndrome
	flail leg	Flail leg syndrome
	SLA demenza	Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis with dementia
	malattia motoneuroni	Motor Neuron Disease / Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis
	SLA atipica	Atypical Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis
	MMN bulbare	Bulbar Motor Neuron Disease / Bulbar Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis
	I moton + APP	Upper Motor Neuron syndrome + Primary Progressive Aphasia
1 MN	Primary Lateral Sclerosis	
MMN spinale	Spinal Motor Neuron Disease / Spinal Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis	

Field	Description	
	SLA familiare?	Familial Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis
	MMN spinale	Spinal Motor Neuron Disease / Spinal Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis
	SLA in accertamento	Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis under diagnosis
	MMN + decadimento	Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis with dementia
	DEMENZA FRONTO TEMPORALE	Frontotemporal Dementia
	mielopatia cervicale?	Spondylotic Cervical Myelopathy
	MMN con VCP	Motor Neuron Disease with VCP mutation / Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis with VCP mutation
	SLA PEG	Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis Percutaneous Endoscopic Gastrostomy
	AAA syndrome	Allgrove Syndrome
7. Data diagnosi	Date of the diagnosis	

Anamnesi (Medical history)

Field	Description	
1. ID	Patient ID	
2. data diagnosi	Date of diagnosis	
3. data esordio	Date of onset	
4. et esordio	Age of onset	
5. data exitus	Date of death	
6. data tracheostomia	Date of tracheostomy	
7. familiarità malattia neurodegenerativa	Family history of neurodegenerative diseases	
8. anti GM1	Antibody levels to ganglioside-monosialic acid	
9. note anti GM1	Values:	
	anti GM1	note anti GM1

Field	Description
	negativi
No	cella vuota
No	negativi
Si	normali
Si	in attesa di referto
Si	positivi
Si	non eseguiti
Si	
Si	<100
Si	debolmente positivi (1:1600)
Si	positivi 5900 BTU
Si	Il paziente ha eseguito dosaggio di anticorpi anti-GM1 e anti-MAG, risultati negativi
10. ID biopsia muscolare	ID number of the biopsy
11. biopsia muscolare	Muscular biopsy performed or not
12.note biopsia muscolare	Outcome of the biopsy
13. liquor	Liquor analysis performed or not
14. storia oncologica	Oncological history
15. rischio erbicidi	Herbicide risk
16. rischio metalli	Metal risk
17. rischio poliomielite	Polio risk
18. rischio sport	Sport risk
19. rischio trauma	Trauma risk
20. rischio trauma elettrico	Electric trauma risk
21. rischio pesticidi	Pesticide risk
22. rischio fumatore	Smoking risk
23. rischio solventi	Solvent risk

Field	Description
24. PEM	Motor Evoked Potentials (PEM) - Motor Evoked Potentials allow us to evaluate the correct functionality of the motor nervous system. These are the responses that can be recorded at a muscular level following electrical or magnetic stimulation of the cerebral cortex or spinal cord
25. RMN cerebrale	Brain MRI diagnosis
	(normale -> brain atrophy false;
	alterato -> brain atrophy true)
26. note RMN cerebrale	Additional free text notes. It is important to consider the free text values.
27. RMN spinale	Spinal MRI diagnosis
28. note RMN spinale	Additional free text notes
29. PET RMN cerebrale	Brain PET MRI diagnosis
30. ubicazione RMN	Anatomical location of the MRI
31. sintomi esordio	Onset symptoms
32. note sintomi esordio	Free text notes on onset symptoms
33. sottotipo	Subtype (see field in the "Anagrafica" sheet)
34. note sottotipo	Subtype notes (see field in the "Anagrafica" sheet)
35. note familiarit	Family history notes
36. note storia oncologica	Oncological history notes
37. COL	Cholesterol
38. CPK	CPK (Creatine Phosphokinase): Enzyme found in the heart, brain, and skeletal muscle. High levels can indicate muscle damage, including from a heart attack.
39. CRE	CRE (Creatinine): A waste product produced by muscles and released into the blood. The kidneys filter creatinine from the blood into the urine. High levels can indicate kidney dysfunction.
40. EMG	EMG: Electromyography, a diagnostic procedure to assess the health of muscles and the nerve cells that control them. It's not a blood test but a part of neurological examinations.

Field	Description
41. GLU	GLU (Glucose): The main sugar found in the blood and the body's primary source of energy. Abnormal levels can indicate diabetes or other health conditions.
42. HB	HB (Hemoglobin): A protein in red blood cells that carries oxygen throughout the body. Abnormal levels can indicate anemia or other blood disorders.
43. K	K (Potassium): An essential electrolyte important for nerve and muscle cell function, especially heart muscle cells. Both high and low levels can be dangerous.
44. MCV	MCV (Mean Corpuscular Volume): A measure of the average size of your red blood cells. It can help diagnose types of anemia.
45. Na	Na (Sodium): An essential electrolyte that helps regulate water balance in and around cells. It's important for nerve and muscle function.
46. PLT	PLT (Platelets): Cell fragments that are crucial for blood clotting. Abnormal levels can indicate a bleeding disorder or bone marrow disease.
47. PROT	PROT (Total Protein): Measures the total amount of protein in the blood and can indicate nutritional status and a variety of diseases.
48. RBC	RBC (Red Blood Cells): Carry oxygen from the lungs to the rest of the body and bring carbon dioxide back to the lungs to be expelled. Counting them can help diagnose or monitor diseases and conditions that affect red blood cells.
49. SID	SID: "Serum Iron", test measuring the amount of iron in the blood.
50. TRIG	TRIG (Triglycerides): A type of fat (lipid) found in your blood. High levels can increase the risk of heart disease.
51. WBC	WBC (White Blood Cells): Part of the immune system and help fight infections. Abnormal levels can indicate an infection, inflammation, or diseases affecting the immune system.
52. ALS 1	ALSFRS-R questionnaire scores
53. ALS 2	ALSFRS-R questionnaire scores

Field	Description
54. ALS 3	ALSFRS-R questionnaire scores
55. ALS 4	ALSFRS-R questionnaire scores
56. Gastrostomia	If the patient has not undergone a gastrostomy (PEG/RIG) the ALS 5b value remains empty, while if the patient has undergone a gastrostomy (PEG/RIG) the ALS 5a field will remain empty
57. ALS 5a	ALSFRS-R questionnaire scores
58. ALS 5b	ALSFRS-R questionnaire scores
59. ALS 6	ALSFRS-R questionnaire scores
60. ALS 7	ALSFRS-R questionnaire scores
61. ALS 8	ALSFRS-R questionnaire scores
62. ALS 9	ALSFRS-R questionnaire scores
63. ALS 10	ALSFRS-R questionnaire scores
64. ALS 11	ALSFRS-R questionnaire scores
65. ALS 12	ALSFRS-R questionnaire scores
66. ALS totale	ALSFRS-R questionnaire total score
67. diario clinico	Clinical diary
68. FVC	<p>FVC (Forced Vital Capacity). Refers to spirometry, a diagnostic test that measures a person's lung capacity and their ability to ventilate.</p> <p><i>FVC (Capacità Vitale Forzata). Fa riferimento alla spirometria, un test diagnostico che misura la capacità polmonare di una persona e la sua capacità di ventilazione.</i></p>
69. Hoffmann dx	The Hoffmann's sign (also known as Hoffmann's reflex) test is a neurological examination procedure used to detect signs of upper motor neuron dysfunction, which could indicate various neurological conditions. A positive result suggests the presence of an upper motor neuron lesion above the level of the spinal cord segment C8. A positive Hoffmann's sign is indicative of issues in the corticospinal tract, which could be due to a variety of neurological disorders.
70. Hoffmann sx	As above

Field	Description
71. labilit emotiva	Rapid and intense changes in one's emotions without apparent causes.
72. lingua fascicola	Neurological examination of the tongue. Tongue - fascicle: Refers to fasciculations, or involuntary contractions of the muscles. They may indicate a neurological disorder or be present in healthy individuals.
73. lingua non sporge	Neurological examination of the tongue. Tongue - not protruding: Indicates difficulty or inability to protrude the tongue, potentially due to a neurological problem involving the nerves or muscles responsible for tongue movement.
74. lingua spinge	Neurological examination of the tongue. Tongue-thrust: Refers to the ability of the tongue to push against resistance, a sign of normal muscle strength.
75. lingua sporge	Neurological examination of the tongue. Tongue - protrudes: Indicates the ability to extend the tongue. Difficulty or deviations may suggest problems with the nerves or muscles that control the tongue.
76. lingua trofismo	Neurological examination of the tongue. Tongue - trophism: Evaluates the health, size and general condition of the muscle tissue of the tongue, identifying atrophy, hypertrophy or other changes.
77. plantare dx	Cutaneous-plantar reflex: Reflex used in neurology to evaluate the integrity of the central nervous system, in particular the corticospinal pathway. When it evokes a response of slow and solemn extension of the big toe associated with the flourishing of the other toes, it is called Babinski's sign and indicates a lesion of the first section of the corticospinal pathway (of the first motor neuron).
78. plantare sx	As above
79. note pneumologia	Notes on pneumology
80. note ROT	Notes on Osteo-Tendon reflexes. General evaluation of reflexes that helps determine the integrity of the nervous system. Upper extremity ROT: Focuses on reflexes found in the upper extremities, such as the bicipital (biceps), triceps (triceps), brachioradialis (forearm), and cubitopronator (forearm) reflex. Evaluation of these reflexes provides information about the functions of the cervical spinal nerves. ROT lower limbs: Affects reflexes located in the

Field	Description
	lower limbs, such as the patellar (knee) reflex and the Achilles (Achilles tendon) reflex. These reflexes help evaluate the functions of the lumbosacral spinal nerves. The presence, absence, or exaggeration of osteotendinous reflexes can indicate various neurological conditions. For example, brisk reflexes may suggest central nervous system injury, while decreased or absent reflexes may indicate problems in the peripheral nervous system.
81. ROT arti superiori	See above for upper limbs.
82. ROT arti inferiori	See above for lower limbs.
83. farmaci	Medications.
84. terapia urgenza minzionale	Urinary urgency therapy.
85. genetica positiva	Flag indicating that genetic testing for the patient was reported as positive.
86. DNA pos	Indicator of positive genetic test.
87. DNA neg	Indicator of negative genetic test.
88. osservazioni emg	Notes on EMG
89. flgblocchicond	Presence of conduction blocks on electromyography
90. flgexitus	Flag Exitus
91. flgfamiliarita	Flag of familiarity (there is familiarity).
92. note liquor	Notes on CSF (liquor).
94. ega	Blood gas analysis (ABG) is a blood test that measures the levels of oxygen (O ₂), carbon dioxide (CO ₂), blood pH, partial pressure of oxygen (PaO ₂), partial pressure of carbon dioxide (PaCO ₂), oxygen saturation (SaO ₂), and bicarbonate (HCO ₃ ⁻). This test is essential for evaluating a patient's respiratory function and acid-base balance.
95. marcia	Evaluation of walk.
96. masseterino	The masseteric reflex is a neuromuscular reflex that involves the masseter muscle, one of the muscles of mastication. This reflex is activated when the chin or jaw region is stimulated, causing the masseter muscle to contract. This reflex is controlled by the trigeminal nerve and when it is lively it indicates a lesion to the bulbar motor neuron.

Field	Description
97. motilitaattiva	Evaluates the motility and coordination of the upper limbs. If you raise your hands above your head/clap your hands above your head, the strength of the abductors of the upper limbs is preserved. The fine movements of the fingers, the grasp and opposition of the fingers indicate the strength and coordination of the intrinsic muscles of the hands.
98. notebio	Free-text notes on laboratory / biological test results, and lifestyle of the patient as recorded by the clinician.
99. pH, pco2, po2, so2	pH, PCO ₂ (Partial Pressure of Carbon Dioxide), PO ₂ (Partial Pressure of Oxygen), SO ₂ (Oxygen Saturation) refer to arterial blood gas analysis, a laboratory test that measures the quantity of oxygen and carbon dioxide in the blood, as well as pH, the concentration of bicarbonate and other gases in arterial blood. This test provides important information on the patient's health status and the correct functionality of the respiratory and circulatory system. It is often prescribed to evaluate the effectiveness of oxygen therapy, monitor patients with respiratory or cardiac diseases.
100. Spirometria	Spirometry